

IoT and YOLO-Based Industrial Security System PPE Detection and Personnel Monitoring

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Abstract—This article presents the development of an industrial security system based on Artificial Intelligence, Computer Vision, and the Internet of Things (IoT), aimed at automatically monitoring the use of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) and performing employee access control. The study contextualizes the problem from the high rates of workplace accidents in Brazil, especially in confined spaces, and highlights the importance of safety regulations such as NR-6 and NR-33. Manual enforcement of PPE use remains flawed, and technologies such as sensors, AI, and IoT networks emerge as more accurate and efficient alternatives. The developed system uses the YOLO11x algorithm for real-time PPE detection, trained on a dataset containing labeled images of helmets, boots, vests, goggles, gloves, masks, and other items. The best results were obtained for the classes person, helmet, vest, and boots, which achieved accuracy above 94%. In addition, the project incorporates facial recognition through the OpenCV and face-recognition libraries, enabling worker identification and automatic access logging. IoT integration is achieved via the HiveMQ MQTT broker, enabling fast communication between the detection system and monitoring platforms. FMEA analysis identified critical failures, such as non-recognition of PPE or improper access release, suggesting preventive measures such as sensor redundancy, calibration, and audits. Tests demonstrated satisfactory performance, though dependent on camera quality, which directly influences detection accuracy. It is concluded that the system represents a significant advance in occupational safety, automating processes and strengthening risk prevention. Future work should focus on improving the dataset, enhancing performance for low-accuracy classes, and adding features such as voice synthesis for compliance alerts.

Index Terms—Computer Vision; Facial Recognition; Occupational Monitoring; Access Control; Industrial Safety.

I. INTRODUCTION

The occurrence of workplace accidents in Brazil still presents alarming figures. Data from the eSocial system of the Ministry of Labor and Employment (MTE) reveal that, in 2023, 2,888 fatal accidents were recorded in the country, of which 373 occurred in the state of São Paulo (Brasil, 2023). Among the different types of accidents, those related to activities in confined spaces stand out for their high severity, presenting a higher proportion of fatalities relative to injuries with leave of absence (1:2) (Naghavi K. et al., 2019).

Although the risks in confined spaces are widely recognized and regulated by international standards — such as OSHA 29 CFR 1910.146 and ANSI/ASSE Z117.1 — and national ones, such as Regulatory Standard No. 33 (NR-33), which

defines a confined space as any environment not designed for continuous occupancy, with limited entry and exit points and the possibility of a hazardous atmosphere (Brasil, 2024), fatal accidents in these environments persist.

In Brazil, occupational safety legislation establishes important parameters for mitigating these risks. NR-6, for example, defines Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), as well as the responsibilities of organizations and workers regarding the supply, use, maintenance, and inspection of these devices (Brasil, 2025). Such measures are aligned with NR-01, which sets out the hierarchy of preventive actions to be adopted in occupational risk management.

Occupational safety, understood as the set of measures aimed at preventing accidents and eliminating unsafe conditions, also involves raising worker awareness and providing instruction on preventive practices (Santos, 2023). However, non-compliance with these standards can result not only in harm to workers' health and lives, but also in economic and reputational losses for organizations. In this context, new technologies have been investigated as complementary strategies to established practices.

Manual enforcement of PPE use presents considerable challenges, being susceptible to failures, inefficiencies, and negligence, which can lead to serious accidents and high costs for companies and society (Caramuru, 2024). Among these technologies, sensors stand out for enabling real-time monitoring of proper PPE use, offering flexibility, versatility, and greater precision in data collection (Caramuru, 2024). Thus, the integration of established regulations with innovative technological solutions may represent a significant advance in accident prevention in high-risk environments such as confined spaces.

Given the complexity and criticality of PPE monitoring, technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and Computer Vision have emerged as effective solutions for automating and optimizing enforcement (Guimarães et al., 2023). In particular, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are widely used for object detection in images, enabling accurate identification of PPE usage (or absence), such as helmets, gloves, footwear, and goggles. Algorithms from the YOLO (You Only Look Once) family, such as YOLOv5 and YOLOv8, are highlighted for their high

speed and accuracy in real-time detection, being preferred for improving user experience and reducing operational costs in monitoring projects (Flôres, 2023). These models are trained and evaluated using metrics such as Mean Average Precision (MAP), demonstrating promising results in PPE classification and accident prevention (Santos, 2023).

Beyond computer vision, the Internet of Things (IoT) provides a comprehensive framework for continuous monitoring and access control, integrating physical devices into intelligent networks (Flôres, 2023). Systems based on Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) enable automatic identification of workers and their PPE, controlling entry and exit in restricted environments (Flôres, 2023). Another approach involves the development of wearable IoT sensors that can be attached directly to PPE to monitor their use in real time, transmitting data via Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) to smartphones acting as gateways and, consequently, to cloud platforms such as ThingSpeak (Guimarães et al., 2023). Optimizing these devices for low energy consumption and overcoming challenges related to limited computational resources, such as those found in microcomputers like the Raspberry Pi, are crucial aspects for the viability and scalability of these solutions (Naghavi K. et al., 2019).

Given the evolution and convergence of these technologies, this article seeks to explore the integration of computer vision and IoT approaches to develop more efficient and autonomous PPE monitoring systems. By analyzing recent advances and remaining challenges, it is proposed to discuss how the combination of these tools can strengthen occupational safety, reduce accidents, and optimize risk management in work environments.

II. METHODS

Facial recognition applied to the occupational environment enables the generation of comprehensive reports on worker attendance, supporting performance analysis and verification of compliance with safety standards. In emergency situations, such as accidents, the technology demonstrates strategic relevance, as it allows for fast and accurate identification of individuals present at the scene — an essential aspect for collective safety and adequate organizational response.

Additionally, the system integrates PPE usage monitoring features, ensuring that employees enter the work environment in compliance with the practices established by the company. The combined incorporation of these technologies contributes to promoting a safer work environment, while also strengthening the organizational culture of responsibility and prevention, prioritizing worker well-being across all activities.

The project therefore represents an advance in safety management and operational effectiveness, aligning with industry best practices and current occupational health and safety regulatory requirements. As it evolves, the system has the potential to be continuously adjusted and improved to meet the specific demands of different work environments, constituting a robust and efficient solution for access control and occupational risk prevention.

III. DEVELOPMENT

A. Environment Setup and Model Training

The implementation of an artificial intelligence system with computer vision was developed based on the YOLO11 technology, which offers high efficiency in object detection, applied with particular attention to PPE items. The dataset used for model training was obtained from the Roboflow platform, containing pre-labeled images of different types of PPE. After dataset selection, it was imported into the Ultralytics Hub, which provided the necessary code for training, organization, and results analysis.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After implementation and execution of the system, the results obtained were satisfactory, demonstrating correct operation in more than 70% of the PPE recognition and facial recognition modules. However, it is worth noting that the system is highly dependent on the hardware used, particularly the camera — a higher image capture quality is capable of doubling identification accuracy.

As shown in the figure above, the goggles item was not computed as it did not function during the testing period; the glove item, even after several training stages, was unable to perform identification; and the boot item requires further refinement, as it frequently recognized sneakers as belonging to the class while failing to identify actual boots, as shown in Figure 3.

Some components such as person and vest (reflective vest) achieved accuracy values close to 1, which is the reference for perfect identification. The contrast between clothing and the environment also has a high degree of significance, including lighting conditions that can either aid or hinder identification, compounded by the resolution of the camera used, which amplifies the overall result.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This article explored the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies to develop an effective supervisory system aimed at monitoring PPE use and controlling access in work environments. The methodology employed, based on computer vision and the YOLO11x algorithm, proved robust for object detection. The model was trained to recognize eight PPE classes and demonstrated overall performance in practical environments, with correct operation in more than 70% of the PPE recognition and facial recognition modules.

The proposed system incorporates not only PPE detection and worker identification, but also risk management functionalities such as access log recording, alert storage in cases of non-compliance, and automatic report updates. Although the general results were achieved, the study highlighted that identification accuracy is highly dependent on the quality of the hardware used, particularly the image capture camera.

In conclusion, the “IoT and YOLO-Based Industrial Security System” represents a significant advance in safety management and operational effectiveness. The integration of

Fig. 1. Validation of facial recognition.

	Edmilson	Matheus	Miguel	Millena	Pedro	ACURÁCIA
SEM	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90%
CAPACETE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	78% - 80%
COLETE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90%
ÓCULOS	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	x
LUVA	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	0%
BOTA	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	50%

Fig. 2. Class identification and accuracy.

regulations (such as NR-6) with innovative technological solutions, including AI and IoT, strengthens occupational safety. For future work, it is recommended to improve the dataset and refine the training models, especially for PPE items with low accuracy, in order to more comprehensively and scalably meet the specific demands of different work environments, as well as the implementation of voice synthesis to signal “compliant” and “non-compliant” status.

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Fig. 3. Test results.

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